
PALYNOLOGICAL ANALYSES OF SEDIMENT FROM NIGER DELTA'S MEREN OIL FIELD WELL 11: INDICATING AGE AND ENVIRONMENT OF DEPOSITION

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Abstract

Palynological analysis was carried out on twenty (20) selected ditch cutting sediments collected from different depths (5130 ft – 6030 ft) of Well 11, Meren oil field, Niger Delta, using the non-acid method. The unwashed ditch cutting samples were initially rinsed to remove drilling mud and then dried at room temperature for 24 hours to avoid agglomeration or clumps of the samples during crushing. The ditch cutting samples were crushed to the size of 250 µm with the aim of exposing more of the sample particles to chemical processes, as well as totally separating all organic constituents.

The analysis was done to delineate the age, depositional environment, maturity of the organic matter, and possible hydrocarbon accumulation.

The analysis revealed the occurrence of *Perchydemitites diderex*, *Retimonocolpites*, *Arecipites exillimuratus*, *Zonocostites ramonae*, *Monoporites annulatus*, *Psilatricolporites crassus*, and *Striaticolpites catatumbus*. These forms indicate environments that are under terrestrial influence, as well as those formed with moderate to high organic matter inputs, usually deposited in a marginal marine environment.

Keywords: Age – Depositional Environment - Agbada Formation · Niger Delta · Hydrocarbon Potential - Palynology.

INTRODUCTION

The Niger Delta is a globally significant hydrocarbon province, and the Meren Field is a critical component of its petroleum system.

Palynological studies in Nigeria are largely confined to the Tertiary Niger Delta (Oboh, 1992). Following the discovery of petroleum resources in the Niger Delta in the late 1950s, the region has attracted numerous studies, but much of the information exist as confidential reports of the companies prospecting for oil and gas in the basin. Palynofacies refer to the total organic content of a sedimentary rock as observed under microscope commonly called kerogen (Combaz, 1964). The main palynofacies in the Niger Delta are structured woody material, opaque organic matter, cuticles, pollens, spores and amorphouse organic matter.

Adopting a palynological preparation of rock sample, the microscopic investigation of palynological matter include; the identification of polynormorphs, structured organic matter (phytoclasts and zooclasts) and unstructured organic matter (amorphous organic matter, gelified materials, resins ambers, solid bitumen) as well as evaluation of the relative abundance, size and state of preservation of constituents. This method is sequel to the work of numerous authors like Combaz,1964; Batten, 2012; Traverse, 1998; Powell *et al.* 1990; Gorin and Steffen, 1991; Tyson, 1995).

Abstracts on Niger Delta geological and palynological studies abound in the literature, but only few full papers have been published (Frankl and Cordry, 1967; Short and Stauble, 1967; Weber, 1971; Oomkens, 1974; Weber and Daukoru, 1975; Evamyet *al.* 1978; Knox and Omatsola, 1989; Oboh, 1992; Haack *et al.* 2000; Hooper *et al.* 2002; Van Heijstet *al.* 2002; Koledoyeet *al.* 2003). Some studies, such as Doust and Omatsola (1990) and Reijerset *al.* (1997) have related the depositional units of the delta to those of the surrounding basins in Southern Nigeria. Most palynological studies are concerned with zonation, age determinations, and correlation.

Aside the determination of age and depositional environment of rock samples through the recovery of palynofacies, the maturity and the associated hydrocarbons can also be detected from the color of the recovered polynomorphs. The microscopic investigation of polynomorphs colors gives the thermal alteration index (TAI) value which indicates that thermally immature polynomorphs are yellowish during diagenesis with TAI value of 1, but changes to orange or yellow-brown during diagenesis with TAI of 2, when the heat is increased, the change to brown during catagenesis with TAI of 3 and then finally changes to black during metagenesis with TAI of 4 and 5 (Staplin, 1969).

Nwachukwu and Chukwura (1985) carried out an organic survey of the Western Niger Delta, where the study area is located (Meren 69), the analysis revealed lack of dinoflagellates which suggest a predominance of terrestrially derived amorphous organic matter in the shale of Agbada Formation which could have sourced the oil in the area.

In a similar study, Olajide, (2014) stresses that mainly shale sediments were deposited in a marginally marine environment under a terrestrial influence as indicated by presence of very rare dinocyst and significant amount of cuticular material. They found the age of the sediments to range from late Oligocene – Mid Miocene age based on the co-occurrence of pantropical stratigraphic markers such as *Zonocostites ramonae* (which first came into existence during the late Oligocene), *Retimonocolpites protrudens* etc.

Chukwura and Nwachukwu (1986), reports that oil pools were discovered at the depth of 1525m in the middle Miocene sandstones held in rollover anticlines associated with

increasing growth faults. Similarly, Konyukhov (2008), observed that Meren field is characterized by depositional belt within the trending fault system that took place during the Tertiary age.

Fig. 1. Geologic map of the Niger Delta. a: The location and geology of the Niger Delta and surrounding basins (Aizebeokhai et al 2011); b: Map of Niger Delta depobelts and structures indicating the study well (Ukpong et al., 2018).

GEOLOGY OF THE STUDY AREA

The study area is located within the Niger Delta, Nigeria. The Niger Delta sedimentary basin is a product of triple junction phenomenon comprising the Gulf of Guinea, South Atlantic Ocean and Benue depression. The Niger delta is one of the world's largest Tertiary delta system and an extremely prolific hydrocarbon province. The Niger Delta is situated on the Gulf of Guinea on the west coast of central Africa and extends throughout the Niger Delta Province as defined by Klett, Ahlbrandt, Schmoker and Dolton 1997. It occupies an area of about 75,000 km² with clastic sequence which reaches a maximum thickness of 9000-12000m of sediment and a total sediment volume of 500,000km³ and a sediment thickness of over 10 km in the basin's depocenter (Kaplan and Baedecker., 1994) between latitude 3°N and 6°N and longitudes 5°E and 8°E. Stratigraphically, the thick sedimentary sequence is made up of three lithostratigraphic units namely; the Benin, Agbada and Akata Formations (Fig2). The Akata Formation is the basal unit, consisting of prodelta marine shale and less than 10% sandstone, deposited in a deep marine setting (Short and Stauble, 1967). Its thickness ranges from 600m to 6000m, while its age ranges from Eocene to Recent. The Akata shales contain a few streaks of sand, possibly turbiditic in origin, and were deposited in holomarine (delta front to deeper marine) environments (Doust and Omatsola, 1990). The Agbada Formation represents the delta front lithofacies, consisting of shoreface and channel sand deposits with minor shale in the upper parts and an alternation of sand and shale of almost equal proportion in the lower part (Short and Stauble, 1967). Its thickness ranges from about 3000m to 4500m, while its age ranges from Eocene to Recent in the northern and offshore areas (Short and Stauble, 1967; Avbovbo, 1978b). The Benin Formation is the uppermost unit, consisting of fluvial gravels and sand occurring from the contemporary delta surface to a depth of about 2134m (7,000ft) (Short and Stauble, 1967). It consists predominantly of massive, highly porous, fresh water bearing sandstones, with local thin shale inter-beds, which are considered to be of braided stream origin (Frankl and Cordry, 1967; Short and Stauble, 1967; Weber and Daukoru, 1975). The debate on the source sediments of the Niger Delta Basin has been ongoing for over four decades, with three schools of thought existing: the Agbada Formation (Frankl and Cordry, 1967; Short and Stauble, 1967; Reed, 1969; Lambert-Aikhionbare and Ibe, 1984), Akata Formation (Weber and Daukoru, 1975; Evamy et al., 1978; Ekweozor and Okoye, 1980), and a combination of both (Ejedawe, 1981; Ejedawe and Okon, 1984; Frost, 1997). The three formations exist in the subsurface of the onshore and offshore of the Niger Delta (Frankl and Cordry, 1967; Weber and Daukoru, 1975; Knox and Omatsola, 1989; Obaje and Okosun, 2013; Short and Stauble, 1967).

Niger Delta stands among the World's best studied Delta complexes because of its economic potentials petroliferous province (Ekweozor and Daukoru 1992; Ekweozor and Okoye 1980; Nyantakyi *et al.* 2014).

The Niger Delta is situated on the Gulf of Guinea on the west coast of central Africa and extends throughout the Niger Delta Province as defined by Klett *et al.* (1997). It is one of the world's largest, deltas, with the sub aerial portion covering about 75,000 km² and extending more than 300 km from apex to the mouth (Doust and Omatsola, 1990). From the Eocene to the present, the delta has prograded southwestward, forming depobelts that represent the most active portion of the delta at each stage of its development (Doust and Omatsola, 1990). According to Kulke (1994), these depobelts, form one of the largest regressive deltas in the world with an area of some 300,000 km². Hospers, (1965) indicated a sediment volume of 500,000 km³, and a sediment thickness of over 10 km in the basin's depocenter (Kaplan *et al.* 1994). The Niger Delta is bounded to the North by the Anambra Basin and the Abakaliki high; to the West by the Dahomey basin and the Benin flank; and to the East by the Calabar

Flank, the Equatorial Guinea Basin, and the Cameroonian volcanic line (Doust and Omatsola, 1990).

It is situated in the Gulf of Guinea and estimated at about 116,000 m² (3000, 000 km²) in area and about 6m (10 km) in depocentre thickness. Niger Basin is the largest basin in the continental margin of the Gulf of Guinea (Kulke, 1994).

Fig. 2: Stratigraphic column showing the three formations of the Niger Delta and seismic display of thickness of the important units (after Corredor et al., 2005).

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The analysis identified the palynofacies and their abundance in the 20 ditch cutting samples retrieved from the strata penetrated by well 11 in the Meren field Western Niger Delta.

The analysis was done to delineate the age, depositional environment, maturity of the organic matter and possible hydrocarbon accumulation.

The Palynological analysis which involves checking the microscopic content of the rock samples includes the following;

- Identification of Polynomorphs
- Identification of unstructured organic matter (Amorphous organic matter (AOM), gelified materials, resins, ambers etc)
- Identification of structured organic matter (phytoclads and zooclads).

- d) Evaluation of relative abundance, size, state of preservation of constituents (Combaz, 1964; Traverse, 1998; Powell *et al.*, 1990; Tyson 1995).

Preparation of Polynomorphs Using the Non-Acid Method

Polynomorphs were extracted using sodium hexametaphosphate six salt $[(\text{NaPO}_3)_6]$ as disaggregating and deflocculating agent. Phosphates in solution have a high ionic charge and even at low concentrations, affect suspension of colloidal particles. The phosphates generally are known as deflocculating, dispersing and peptizing reagents. They reduce the coherent nature of the clay because phosphate ions are strongly adsorbed into the clay particles, which break up because of the high ionic charges. The surface charges prevent any reflocculation of the clay. This analysis (Fig 3) adopted the prototype work of Blendon *et al.*, 2007, this is the most feasible given the study objectives.

The following steps were taken for the recovery of polymorphs using the aforementioned salt $[(\text{NaPO}_3)_6]$;

- Indurated samples were crushed to pea size
 - a) 20g of each sample were weighed and soaked with distilled water in a container
 - b) Two spoons of hexametaphosphate six salt $[(\text{NaPO}_3)_6]$ was measured into each soaked sample, and were stirred for twenty minutes and left overnight.
 - c) These samples were washed clean through 10μ sieve and the residue poured into an EDTA (ethylenediaminetetracetic acid) bottle.
 - d) The residue was pipette and dropped on rectangular cover slips which were later placed on hot plate for onward drying.
 - e) The dried cover slips were glued to biological slides using Norland adhesive and allowed to dry under the sun.
 - f) These slides were viewed with an Olympus CHB binocular microscope and photomicrograph of observed form were taken and documented.

Fig 3: Work Flow Diagram for Palynological Analysis

Thermal Alteration Index (TAI)

The microscopic examination of polynomorphs color which is termed thermal alteration index according to standard rating scheme for thermal alteration index of polynomorphs

(Table 1), shows how maturity of source rocks can be ascertained through change in color of palynomorphs contained in the rock sample.

Table 1: Thermal Alteration Rating for Polynomorphs (after Staplin., 1969).

Thermal Alteration Index(TAI)	Color of organic matter	Associated hydrocarbons
None	Yellow	Liquid hydrocarbon to dry gas
Slight	Orange to brownish yellow	Liquid hydrocarbon to dry gas
Moderate	Brown	Liquid hydrocarbon to dry gas
Strong	Black	Dry gas
Severe	Black	Dry gas to none

The recovered palynological assemblage consists of pollen, spore, some cuticle materials, (well preserved structured leaf cuticles) and amorphous organic matter (Table2), (Plate 1-3).

They include:

- i. *Perchydemittites diderex*
- ii. *Retimonocolpites*
- iii. *Arecipites exillimuratus*
- iv. *Zonocostites ramonae* (Germeraad et al., 1968)
- v. *Monoporites annulatus* (Van der Hammen, 1954)
- vi. *Psilatricolporites crassus* (Van der Hammen and Wijstra, 1964)
- vii. *Striaticolpites catatumbus* (Germeraad et al., 1968)
- viii. *Ephedripites* sp.
- ix. *Tricolpites* (Bankole et al., 2014)
- x. *Pseudorabbi*
- xi. *Laevigatosporites* sp. (Oloto, 1994)
- xii. *Fusfomiisporites*
- xiii. *Leiotriletes* sp. (Durugbo et al., 2010)
- xiv. *Echiperipotes* (Van der Hammen and Wijstra, 1964)
- xv. *Auricolopollenites simplex* (Germeraad et al., 1968)
- xvi. *Proxaperites oppercultatus* (Legoux, 1978)

Table 2: Palynofacies Analysis of Sediment from well 11 Meren Oil Field

Depth (feet)	Perchydermites Dideres	Retimonocolpites	Arecipitesexillimura tus us	Zonocastic romonae	Monoporites annulatus	Psilatricolporitessp	Striatricolporitessp	Ephedritripitessp	Tricolpitessp	Pseudorabbisp	Laevigatosporites	Fusfomispores sp	Leiotrititessp	Echperiporites	Proxaperites opperculatus	Auricolopollenite simplex
5130	4			5	3		1			4			7		2	1
5220						9		7			3	6		4		
5280		6	2		1				8	5			4			4
5340				2		15	4	9				2		6	3	
5370	7		8	11					11	7						
5430	8	1		4	7		6				5		1	3		7
5470						21		6		9		9				
5520			3	7					13							
5580							2	9			3		5	21		9
5640	1			8	6	1						11			1	
5680		2	7						7							
5720					10		13	5		21		4	3	16		
5790	3			3		2					4			4		21
5810		5			9		1		6							
5850			5					10		14			8		4	
5890				6	4	6					5	8		1		
5910				1	3		4		3							13
5940	6	2						11		12		2	5		13	
6000			4	5	1	4			3		1			4		
6030	2	4			5		3			3						3

SLIDES OF RECOVERED POLYMORPHS

PLATE 1

1
Perchydermites Dideres

2
Retimonocolpites

3
Arecipites exillimuratus

4
Zonocastic romonae

5
Monoporites annulatus

6
Psilatricoporites sp

7
Striatricolporites sp

8
Ephedripites sp

Plate 1a: Photomicrographs of recovered Palynomorphs (x200)

PLATE 1 cont'nd

Plate 1b: Photomicrographs of Recovered Palynomorphs (x200)

SLIDES OF RECOVERED PALYNOFACIES

PLATE 2a

Plate 2a Types of Recovered Palynofacies (x200)

Fig. a-f: Black palynodebris with some Brownish Amorphous organic matter

PLATE 2b

g

h

i

j

k

l

Plate 2b Types of recovered Palynofacies (x200)

Fig. i, j and k: Brownish amorphous organic matter with black pytoclasts

Fig. g, h and l: Some palynofacies with Amorphous organic matter

PLATE 3

Plate 3 Types of Recovered Palynofacies (x200)

Fig i - vi Brownish to black palynodebris with some cuticles.

Palynological Age

The age of the recovered palynomorphs was determined based on their occurrence and general distribution within the studied well with reference to Niger Delta Palynomorphs atlas produced by Oboh-Ikuenobe *et al.*, 2005 Peters *et al.*, 2005., (Table 3). The palynomorphs within the studied interval include; *Striatotricolporites sp.*, *Psilatricolporites sp.*, *Monoporites annulatus*, *Perchydermites diderexi*, *Fusformisporites pseudorabbi*, *Laevigatosporites sp.*, *Leiotriletes sp.*, *Proxaperities operculatus*, *Zonocostic romanae*, *Arecipites exillmuratus*, *Ephedripites sp.*, *Tricolpites sp.*, *Echiperipoites sp.*, *Numupollis neogenicus*.

Laevigatosporites sp. and *Leiotriletes sp.* are of species Miocene age (Oboh, 1992). *Zonocostites ramonae* is a mangrove sp. which evolved in Nigeria in the Oligocene age till recent but frequently occurred in the Mid-Miocene assemblage. *Echiperipoites sp.* occurs commonly during the Miocene age. (Oboh-Ikuenobe *et al.*, 2005). *Arecipites exillmurtus* is an early-Miocene specie.

Striatricolpites sp. is a late Oligocene to middle Miocene specie but commonly occur in the Miocene assemblage *Monoporites annulatus* and *Perchydermites diderexi* which

commonly occur during the Miocene age but occurred in abundance evolved during the Middle Eocene to recent, while *Psilatricolporites sp.* occur in the Early Miocene assemblage but frequently occur from Late Oligocene to Early Miocene age.

Proxapertites operculatus, *Fusiformisporites sp.*, *Retimonocolporites sp.*, and *Pseudorabbi sp.* which appeared very few in the well are of Late Oligocene to Early Oligocene ages but frequently occur during the Mid-Oligocene and Late Oligocene ages respectively and so cannot be used to determine the age of the studied samples.

The result shows that the samples within the studies interval based on occurrence indicate Early Miocene to Late Miocene age.

The result shows that the samples within the studies interval based on occurrence indicate Early Miocene to Late Miocene age.

Table 3: Palynomorphs/Age of Evolution and Real Age (Obboh-Ikuenobe *et al.*, 2005 Peters *et al.*, 2005).

Recovered Palynomorphs	Age of Evolution	Age of Palynomorph
Zonocastic ramonae	Oligocene-recent	Mid Miocene
Stritricolporites sp.	Late Oligocene-mid Miocene	Miocene
Psilatricolporites sp.	Late Oligocene to early Miocene	Early Miocene
Monoporites annulatus /perchydermites diderexi	Mid Miocene to recent	Miocene age
Arecipites exillimuratus. Echhiperiporotes sp. Laevigatosporites sp./Leiotriletes sp.	Tertiary specie	Early Miocene
Proxaporites operculatus, Auriculopollenites sp. Retimonocolporites sp.	Late Eocene to early Oligocene	Late Eocene Early Eocene Early Oligocene

Determination of Maturity using Palynomorphs

The microscopic investigation of palynomorphs colour is termed Thermal Alteration index (TIA) (Table 4). The recovered palynomorphs in the area of study appeared to be orange to yellowish-brown, brownish to dark brown and then dark brown to black colours when viewed with microscope. This corresponds with the thermal alteration index values of 2 for orange to yellow, 2/3 for yellow to brownish and 3 for brownish to black.

Table 4.9 shows that the samples are immature at 4210ft but as the depth increases with temperature at 5520ft, the samples began to get mature as the recovered palynomorphs began to change colour from brown to dark brown and the liquid hydrocarbon began to change into dry gas. But at greater depth of 8830ft, the recovered palynomorphs began to change colour from dark brown to black thereby transforming into gas.

Table 4: Thermal Alteration Index Rating/Evaluation for well 11

Depth (ft)	Thermal Alteration index (TIA)	Colour	Associated Hydrocarbons	Maturity Stage
4210	2	Orange to brownish-yellow	Liquid hydrocarbon to dry gas	Immature
5520	2/3	Brown to dark brown	Liquid hydrocarbon to dry gas	Mature
8830	3	Dark brown to black	Liquid hydrocarbon to dry gas	Mature

CONCLUSION

The microscopic view of palynomorphs colour revealed that the source rocks are capable of yielding gas as the change gradually to dark colour just as the palynomorphs at Depth (5970ft) have colour ranging from brown to dark brown which indicates maturity and at the Depth of (5370ft) have orange to yellowish colour indicating immaturity and early maturity of source rocks within the formation. This confirms with the work of Staplin 1969 which stipulates that palynomorphs with orange to brownish yellow are immature, those with brown to black colours are mature (Staplin, 1969).

Based on the occurrence of *striatricolporites sp.*, *psilatricolporites sp.*, *Zonocostites ramonae*, *Perchydermites diderexi*, *Monoporites annulatus*, *Echiperipoites etc.*, it shows that the sediments were deposited during the Early Miocene to late-Miocene. The palynological assemblage is dominated by pollen/spores, structured cells and amorphous organic matter consists of well preserved and divers taxa and is characterized by dense lowland vegetation. This agrees with the work of Nwachukwu *et al.*, 1984.

The paleoenvironment revealed from the palynofacies analysis from the sediments in the study area are

- i.** Terrestrial origin under nearshore dyoxic-anoxic environment
- ii.** Non-marine or nearshore environment under oxic condition
- iii.** Fluvio-deltaic/nearshore (proximal shelf) under oxic condition and low preservation rates
- iv.** Marginal marine under a proximal dyoxi-suboxic environment

REFERENCES

- Aizebeokhai, A.P and Olayinka, I., Structural and Stratigraphic Mapping of Emi Field, Offshore Niger Delta, Journal of Geology and Mining Research, Vol. 3, No. 2, 2011, pp 25-38.
- Bankole S.I., 2014. Palynology and stratigraphy of three deep wells in the Neogene Agbada Formation, Niger Delta, Nigeria. Implications for petroleum exploration and paleoecology. Technische Universität, Berlin [Ph.D. thesis].
- Batten, D.J. (2012) Palynofacies analysis. In Jones, T.P., Rosse N.P., Eds, Fossil Plants and Sp.
- Blandon, A., Parra, N., Gorin, G.E., Arango, F. (2007). Adapting palynological preparation methods in Subbituminous and bituminous coals from and bituminous coals from Colombia to improve palynofacies and hydrocarbon source rock evaluation. International Journal of Coal Geology. 73
- Combaz, A. 1964. Les palynofacies. Revue Micro paleont., Paris, 7, 205-2 18.
- Controlling depositional patterns in the south-central Niger Delta, West Africa. Journal of Structural Geology, 24: 847–859.
- Corredor F, Shaw JH, Bilotti F (2005) Structural styles in the deepwater fold and thrust belts of the Niger Delta. AAPG Bulletin 89:753–780
- Doust H., Omatsola E.M. (1990) Niger Delta. In: Edwards J.D., Santogrossi P.A. (eds) Divergent/passive Margins Basins. *American Association of Petroleum Geologist Memoir, Tulsa*, pp 239–248.
- Ekweozor C.M., Okoye N.V., (1980) Petroleum source–bed evaluation of Tertiary Niger Delta. *Am Assoc Pet Geol Bull.* **64**: 1251–1259.
- Ekweozor, &Adegoke (1992). Organic geochemistry of the Tertiary sediments from the Niger Delta, Nigeria. *Organic Geochemistry*, 18(6), 829-844.
- Evamy, B.D., Haremboure, J., Kamerling, P., Knaap, W.A., Molloy, F.A., Rowlands, P.H., (1979). Hydrocarbon habitat of Tertiary Niger Delta. *American Association of Petroleum Geologist Bulletin***62**, PP 1-39.
- Frankl, E. J. and Cordry, E. A. (1967). The Niger Delta oil Province-Recent Development Onshore and Offshore: Proceeding 7th World Petroleum Congress. Mexico City. P 195209.
- Germeraad, J.H., Hopping, C.A. and Muller, J. (1968) Palynology of Tertiary Sediments from Tropical Areas. *Review of Palaeobotany and Palynology*, **6**, 189-348.
- Gorin and Steffen. (1991). Organic Facies as a Tool for Recording Eustatic Variation in Marine Fine Grained Carbonates – Example of the Bervasian Stratotype.

- Haack R.C., Sundararaman P., Diedjomahor J.O., Xiao H., Gant N.J., May E.D., Kelsch K. (2000). Niger Delta petroleum systems, Nigeria, in M. R. Mello and B. J. Katz, eds., Petroleum systems of South Atlantic margins. *AAPG Bull* **73**: 213-231.
- Kaplan, A., Baedeker, 1994. Tectonic map of the world, panel 10: Tulsa, American Association of Petroleum Geologists, scale 1: 10,000,000.
- Klett, T.R., Ahlbrandt, T.S., Schmoker, J.W. and Dolton, G.L. (1997). Ranking of the world's oil and gas provinces by known petroleum volumes: U. S. Geological Survey Open-File Report 97-463, CD-Rom.
- Knox, G. J. and Omotsola, E. M. (1989) Development of the Cenozoic Niger Delta in terms of the escalator regression model and impact on hydrocarbon distribution. In Vander Linden.
- Koledoye, B.A., Aydin, A., and May, E. (2003). A new process-based methodology for analysis of shale smear along normal faults in the Niger Delta. American Association of Petroleum Geologists Bulletin, 87: 445–463.
- Konyukhov, A.I., Pericontinental Petroliferous Basins Atlantic Ocean, *Litol. Polezen. Iskop.*, 2008, vol. 43, no.3, pp.227-245
- Kulke, H. (1994). Nigeria. In: kulke (ed). Regional Petroleum geology of the world. Part 11: Africa, America, Australia and Antarctica, pp. 143-172. Belin, GebruderBorntraeger
- Legoux, O., 1978, Quelques especes de pollen caracteristiques du Neogene du Nigeria: Bulletin des Centres de Recherches Exploration Production Elf-Aquitaine, v. 2, p. 265-317.
- Nwachukwu J.I., and Chukwura P.I. (1986) Organic matter of the Agbada formation in Niger Delta Nigeria. *Am Asso Petrol Geol Bull.* **70**: 48–55.
- Nyantakyi EK, Hu WU, Borkloe JK, Nagre RD, Frimpong IK (2014) Geochemical Investigation of Potential Source Rocks for Agbada Formation, Osioka South Area, Western Niger Delta. *Niger Geosci.* **4** (1): 13–22
- Obaje, S. O. and Okosun, E. A. (2013). Planktic foraminiferal biozonation and correlation of XY-1 field, offshore Western Niger Delta, Nigeria. *International Journal of Science and Technology* 3(3) 2013.
- Oboh, F.E., (1992). Middle Miocene palaeoenvironments of the Niger Delta. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 92, 55–84.
- Oboh-Ikuenobe, F.E., Obi C.G., Carlos A. J., 2005. Lithofacies, Palynofacies, and sequence stratigraphy of paleogene strata in southeastern Nigeria. *Jour.Of African Earth science.* V. 41 P. 79-101
- Olajide (2014). Well log sequence Stratigraphic and Palynological Analysis of Late Miocene to Pliocene Agbada Formation, Southwestern Niger Delta Basin, Nigeria. *Review of Environment and Earth Sciences*, 1(2): pp 77-98.

- Oloto I.N. (1994) Nigerian Maastrichtian to Miocene Dinflagellate and Miosporebiozonation – A Summary. *Journal of Mining and Geology*,; 30(1), 61-73
- Oomkens, E., (1974), Lithofacies relations in the late Quaternary Niger delta complex: *Sedimentology*, v. **21**, p. 195-222.
- Reijers, T., Petters, S. and Nwajide, C (1997). The Niger Delta Basin. *Sedimentary Basins of the World*, 3, Pp.151-172 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1874-5997\(97\)80010-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1874-5997(97)80010-X)
- Short K.C., Stauble A.J. (1967). Outline of the geology of the Niger Delta. *Am Asso Petrol Geol Bull.* **51**: 761–779.
- Staplin, F. L. (1969). Interpretation of thermal history from color of particulate organic matter - a review. *Palynol.*, Austin, 1, 9-18.
- Traverse, A. (1998). Palaeopalynology. *Unwin Hyman* 600pp.
- Tyson, R.I. (1995). Sedimentary Organic matter. *Chapman and Hall*, 615pp.
- Ukpong, A.J., Anyanwu, T.C. (2018). Foraminiferal distribution, stratigraphy & palaeoenvironment of the U-12 well, Niger Delta Basin, Nigeria. *Intern. J. Sci. Res. Develop.* 6 (5), 1043-1050.
- Van der Hammen, T. and Wijmstra, T.A. (1964). A palynological study on the Tertiary and Upper Cretaceous of British Guiana. *Leidse. Geologische Mededelingen* 30:18-241.
- Van der Hammen, T. (1954). El desarrollo de la flora Colombiana en los periodos geologicos, Maestrichtiana hasta Terciario mass inferior; *BoletinGeologico.* 2(1): 49-106
- Van Heijst, M.W.I. M, Postma, G., Van Kersteren, W.P., de Jongh, R.G. (2002). Control of syndepositional faulting on systems tract evolution across growth faulted shelf margins: An analog experimental model of the Miocene Imo River field, Nigeria. *American Association of Petroleum Geologists Bulletin* 86: 1335-1366.
- Weber K.J. (1971) Sedimentological aspects of oil fields in the Niger Delta. *Geologieen Mynbouw.* **50** (59–576):1971.